

Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking on Problematic Internet Use in Unmarried Early Adults

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ABSTRACT

The psychosocial development stage of early adulthood is intimacy versus isolation. Intimacy can be obtained through marriage. Many early adults cannot fulfill these stages, so they experience social isolation, which results in Loneliness, so individuals use the Internet as an escape media. Increased Internet use will cause problematic Internet use, where individuals cannot control themselves not to access the Internet, ultimately providing negative outcomes in everyday life. In addition, problematic Internet use is also often associated with Sensation-Seeking. This study aims to explore the role of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking and their association with problematic Internet use in a sample of unmarried early adults. This study is a quantitative study using A Rasch-type Loneliness Scale by Gierveld & Tilburg (2006) with a reliability of 0.840, Arnett Inventory of Sensation-Seeking Scale (AISS) by Arnett (1994) with a reliability of 0.733, and The Generalized Problematic Internet Use Scale 2 (GPIUS2) by Caplan (2010) with a reliability of 0.903. Subjects in the study were selected using a purposive sampling technique totaling 111 unmarried early adults aged 22-33 years who are active in accessing social media in their daily lives. Hypotheses were analyzed using multiple regression analysis.

Keywords: Loneliness; Sensation-Seeking; Problematic Internet use; Unmarried early adulthood

INTRODUCTION

Early adulthood is when an individual's personality tends to be stable and able to make their own choices (Batara & Kristianingsih, 2020). In general, this stage is full of risks and instability because early adulthood is a transition from adolescence, which is still dependent on parents, to an independent adult (Dewi & Ginanjar, 2019). Amru and Ambarini (2021) added that early adult individuals are faced with demands that have heavier responsibilities, such as work or career demands and financial-related problems. In addition, early adulthood needs to fulfill the need to avoid psychosocial crises; as Havighurst said, the task of psychosocial development of early adult individuals is to find and choose a life partner who is compatible with themselves, who can understand their thoughts and feelings to then proceed with marriage or building a family (Putri, 2019).

Based on data obtained by the Badan Pusat Statistik in the publication of Indonesian Youth Statistics for 2023, the development of the percentage of married and unmarried youth is contradictory. The percentage of married young people is decreasing, while the number of unmarried young people is increasing. Of the total population of Indonesian youth, the majority, namely 68.29%, are unmarried, consisting of 78.20% male and 58.15% female (BPS.go.id, 2023). This data shows that the majority of early adults in Indonesia are unmarried.

According to Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, achievement in early adulthood is the stage of intimacy versus isolation. At this stage, early adult individuals try to gain intimacy, which can be achieved by establishing interpersonal relationships with other people in an intimate, warm, communicative manner and making commitments to others. Success at this stage will determine the individual's ability to adapt (Xia et al., 2018). Suppose this is not fulfilled or the individual fails to go through these stages. In that case, they will experience isolation, namely feeling excluded from other people, blaming themselves for feeling different, and lonely. Not fulfilling the need to have an intimate relationship with the opposite sex can cause mental shock for single individuals (Huda, 2012; Sari & Listiyandini, 2015).

Erik Erikson and Havighurst said that adulthood is the period when individuals experience the most lonely feelings. Loneliness that occurs in early adulthood occurs because an individual has not been able to establish a relationship at a more serious level with the opposite sex, primarily through marriage. As explained by Gierveld (in Myers & Twenge, 2017), in early adulthood, Loneliness is often experienced by unmarried people. Russell (1996) defines Loneliness as social relationships that do not match what is desired, including feelings of anxiety, depression, and the perception of a person's lack of social relationships. This Loneliness results from the individual's unpleasant feelings regarding the lack of meaningful social relationships (Hawkley & Cacioppo, 2010). For some people, Loneliness can be accepted as usual, but for some people, it can be a deep sadness (Winningham & Pike, in Astutik et al. 2019). Social isolation is one of the strongest predictors of Loneliness and has a negative effect on an individual's mental health and well-being. Lack of social skills due to social isolation worsens the individual's Loneliness.

Loneliness reflects an individual's unsatisfied desire to connect closely with others and engage in meaningful relationships, an individual failure in social life that is important for human well-being (Zammuner, 2008). Loneliness is identified as a specific risk factor for physical and emotional health, including anxiety, depression, alcoholism, suicidal thoughts,

cognitive decline, obesity, decreased immune response, and premature death (Cacioppo & Grippo, 2015). Loneliness is correlated with lower cognitive function, having one or more chronic health conditions, experiencing a stroke, depressive symptoms, sleep disturbances, sleep-related disorders, and low life satisfaction (Peltzer & Pengpid, 2019). Apart from that, Loneliness is also known to have a high involvement in unhealthy behavior such as addiction or addiction (Okruzsek et al., 2020). Loneliness can be the reason why individuals tend to prefer indirect communication and use the Internet as a place for regular communication. This can certainly have an impact on increasing the amount of time spent using the Internet, which, if used excessively, will be classified as Internet addiction, which some experts also call pathological Internet use, Internet dependency, and problematic Internet use (Spada, 2014).

Shapira et al. (2003) explained that PIU is closely related to Internet addiction. However, several studies show that there are differences between PIU and Internet addiction. The main difference lies in Internet use characteristics in the circumstances that occur. In PIU, excessive Internet use involves psychosocial and cognitive-behavioral problems. Whereas in Internet addiction, overuse of the Internet may be accompanied by pathological assumptions, including other congenital pathological disorders. Caplan (2010) added that Internet addiction tends to be a pathological condition, while PIU is a psychosocial problem that is not pathological but involves cognitive-behavioral.

Problematic Internet use is a term encompassing specific Internet contexts like chat rooms, email, and social networks such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, TikTok, or other similar platforms. As Rahmawati et al. (2020) pointed out, the lack of control over Internet use can lead to problematic Internet use. This issue, characterized by various Internet usage patterns that influence individual cognition and behavior, can have significant negative outcomes in their lives (Davis, 2001).

According to the 2023 Indonesian Internet Profile, the number of people connected to the Internet reached 215.62 million people out of a total population of 275.77 million people in Indonesia. This shows an increase during the 2022-2023 period, which is shown by the increase in the percentage of the population accessing the Internet in 2022, from around 77.02% to 78.19% in 2023. It was also found that the majority of people accessing the Internet are in the 35-54 year age range, amounting to 33.67%, then followed by the age range 19-34 at 32.09%, and the age range 13-18 years with a percentage of 12.15%. The reasons for using the Internet are varied; the most significant percentage was found to be the reason for using the

Internet as a means to access social media (including accessing Facebook/ Whatsapp/ Telegram/ Line/ Twitter/ Instagram/ Youtube/ and others.) (APJII, 2023).

The Internet can be an escape medium to overcome Loneliness. Erdogan (2008) believes that increasing Internet use can reduce levels of Loneliness. This is because the Internet can provide emotional support and fun activities. Previous research shows that individuals who feel lonely are associated with increased excessive Internet use (Skues et al., 2016).

Lonely individuals will usually tend to search for sensations outside the real social environment by using virtual activities, which can lead to excessive Internet use. According to research by Armstrong et al. (in Widyanto and Griffiths, 2007), someone with Sensation-Seeking behavior tends to be unable to control high Internet use. Surfing the Internet or engaging in online activities is widely seen as a form of technological adventure. Therefore, it can be considered a form of Sensation-Seeking (Lin & Tsai, 2002).

According to Zuckerman (1994), Sensation-Seeking is the search for new, complex, vivid sensations and experiences and opportunities to take risks, which can be physical, social, and financial. Sensation-Seeking reflects the potential to take risks and the quality of search intensity and novelty in seeking experiences, which can be expressed in various areas of a person's life (Annalakshmi et al., 2020), such as accessing the Internet. Most literature studies on Sensation-Seeking and Internet use were conducted with college student samples (Dalbesar et al., 2015; Jang et al., 2018).

Based on the explanation above, the psychosocial needs of unmarried early adults due to Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking can be met directly or indirectly, one of which is through the use of digital technology, especially the Internet which can function as a connecting function, helping individuals increase their social capital. (Boursier, et al. 2020; Nadkarni & Hofmann 2012). Over time, the social need exacerbated by Loneliness evolves, with the Internet increasingly assuming the role of a medium for Sensation-Seeking, filling the void in an individual's life.

Many previous studies have discussed problematic Internet use and its association with Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking separately. Researchers are interested in studying this issue more deeply. This is because there has been no research that discusses Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking and their influence on problematic Internet use simultaneously using a sample of unmarried early adult individuals. Thus, this study aims to explore more deeply the influence of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking, as well as their association with problematic

Internet use in a sample of unmarried early adult social media users. Kim (2017); Şentürk et al (2021) found that unmarried early adult individuals are more prone to excessive Internet use than other groups due to higher levels of suicidal ideation, planning, anxiety, and Loneliness.

METHODS

This research is a quantitative study with data collection techniques using a questionnaire equipped with an identity sheet and three scales: the Loneliness scale, Sensation-Seeking scale, and problematic Internet use scale. The three scales use a 5-point Likert scale system, where respondents will be asked to choose one of five alternative answers. In addition, the identity sheet consists of gender, age, the most frequently used social media, and the length of time participants access the Internet in one day. The questionnaire in this study was given in Google Forms.

This study involved 111 unmarried early adult social media users as participants, including 44 men and 67 women, aged 22 to 33 years. The sampling technique was determined by non-probability sampling technique, namely purposive sampling, with predetermined criteria, namely Men and Women with an age range of 20-40 years in accordance with what Papalia and Feldman (2014) stated that the age range of young adults is between the ages of 20 to 40 years, unmarried status, and actively using social media in daily life.

The first measurement tool is the Loneliness scale. Loneliness is an unpleasant feeling towards situations experienced by individuals based on subjective experiences where the number of relationships with others is smaller than expected or closeness with someone who is expected does not match the reality that occurs (Gierveld & Tilburg, 2006). The Loneliness scale used is A Rasch-Type Loneliness by Gierveld and Tilburg (2006), consisting of 11 items with six items of emotional Loneliness dimensions and five items of social Loneliness dimensions with reliability that has been tested by researchers of 0.84. One of the Loneliness scale items is "I feel often rejected by people around me." The dimensions of Loneliness, according to Gierveld & Tilburg (2006), are:

- a) Emotional Loneliness arises when a person does not have intimate relationships with other people.
- b) Social Loneliness arises when a person does not integrate himself into his life. It can make a person feel alienated, bored, and anxious.

The second measuring instrument in this study is the Sensation-Seeking scale. The scale used is the Arnett Inventory of Sensation-Seeking Scale (AISS) by Arnett (1994), which consists of 20 items with 10 novelty dimension items and 10 intensity dimension items with a researcher-tested reliability of 0.733. One of the Sensation-Seeking scale items is "Standing on the edge of a high cliff and looking down is fun." The dimensions of Sensation-Seeking, according to Arnett (1994), are:

- a) Novelty is the need for stimulation and new experiences.
- b) Intensity is the need for stimulation and experiences that provide intense sensations and sensory input.

The third measuring instrument in this study is the problematic Internet use scale. The scale used is The Generalized Problematic Internet Use Scale 2 (GPIUS2) by Caplan (2010), consisting of 15 items with three items of POSI dimension, three items of mood regulation dimension, three items of cognitive preoccupation dimension, three items of compulsive Internet use, and three items of negative outcomes dimension with a reliability of 0.903. One of the PIU scale items is "When I am offline, I find it difficult to resist going online." The dimensions of problematic Internet use, according to Caplan (2010), are:

- a) POSI (Preference for Online Social Interaction) is the belief that a person feels safer, more confident, and more comfortable in interpersonal relationships online than face-to-face.
- b) Mood regulation, is a strategy or way to divert anxiety that exists in a person through the use of the Internet.
- c) Cognitive Preoccupation, obsessive thoughts about the Internet, thoughts of constantly using the Internet
- d) Compulsive Internet use, someone who cannot control impulses related to the Internet, resulting in compulsive behavior towards Internet use.
- e) Negative outcomes, the impact felt by a person due to uncontrolled Internet use.

The data analysis technique used to test the hypothesis in this study is multiple regression analysis, assisted by the IBM SPSS Statistics Version 25 for Windows computer programs. The assumption tests used are normality, linearity, and multicollinearity tests. Meanwhile, other descriptive data are presented using percentage calculations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Data

Findings related to demographic data can be seen in Table 1. Data exposure in Table 1 contains data regarding early adult unmarried social media users, age, duration, and time commonly used in accessing social media. Based on the exposure in Table 1, it can be seen that out of a total of 111 unmarried early adult subjects, 56 subjects can use a long time on social media in one day, reaching more than 6 hours online, and they usually use it more actively at night. This can happen because, in the morning to evening, early adults will spend their time at work so that after returning home from work, early adult individuals tend not to do activities and will bring up feelings of Loneliness, which leads them to choose to use social media to eliminate these feelings of Loneliness. Morahan-Martin and Schumacher (in Zanah & Rahardjo, 2020) state that individuals who experience Loneliness tend to prefer online communication because they feel comfortable and enjoy the freedom of anonymity. Excessive use of social media in lonely individuals is intended as a means of self-disclosure and is one way of coping strategies in reducing feelings of Loneliness itself because self-disclosure done online is more quickly accepted than interacting face-to-face. In addition, social media is also a place to form intimacy with others and conduct virtual interactions in dealing with and reducing negative feelings, such as Loneliness (Krisnadi & Adhandayani, 2022).

Table 1

Demographic Data Description

Description	Total	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	44	39.6
Female	67	60.4
Age		
22-24	51	45,95
25-27	47	42,34
28-30	10	9,00
31-33	3	2,70
Duration in using social media in one day		
< 3 hours	29	26.1
3 – 6 hours	26	23.4
> 6 hours	56	50.5
Time spent accessing social media		
Morning	5	4.5
Daytime	19	17.1
Afternoon	7	6.3
Night time	80	72.1

Overview of Subject Categories on Each Variable

Based on the results of descriptive data analysis displayed in Table 2 and Loneliness categorization data displayed in Table 3, the key finding of this study is that respondents, on average, have moderate Loneliness categorization with a percentage of 57.66%.

Table 2

Data from descriptive statistical analysis

Variables	Empirical Mean	Standard deviation
<i>Loneliness</i>	34,59	7,33
<i>Sensation-Seeking</i>	63,04	13,33
<i>Problematic Internet Use</i>	42,36	10.815

Table 3

Loneliness data categorization

Categorization	Score range	Total (n)	Percentage
Very Low	$X \leq 18,34$	2	1,80%
Low	$18,34 < X \leq 25,67$	16	14,41%
Moderate	$25,67 < X \leq 40,33$	64	57,66%
High	$40,33 < X \leq 47,66$	24	21,62%
Very High	$X \geq 47,66$	5	4,50%
Total (n)		111	100%

Based on the results of descriptive data analysis displayed in Table 2 and Sensation categorization in Table 4, it can be seen that respondents in this study have an average Sensation-Seeking categorization with a percentage of 83.79%.

Table 4

Sensation-Seeking Data Categorization

Categorization	Score range	Total (n)	Percentage
Very low	$X \leq 33,34$	0	0,00%
Low	$33,34 < X \leq 46,67$	5	4,50%
Moderate	$46,67 < X \leq 73,33$	93	83,79%
High	$73,33 < X \leq 86,66$	12	10,81%
Very high	$X \geq 86,66$	1	0,90%
Total (n)		111	100%

Based on the results of the descriptive data analysis displayed in Table 2 and the categorization of problematic Internet use in Table 5, it can be seen that the respondents in this

study, on average, have a moderate problematic Internet use categorization with a percentage of 63.06%.

Table 5

Categorization of Problematic Internet Use Data

Categorization	Score range	Total (n)	Percentage
Very low	$X \leq 25$	7	6,31%
Low	$25 < X \leq 35$	21	18,92%
Moderate	$35 < X \leq 55$	70	63,06%
High	$55 < X \leq 65$	10	9,01%
Very high	$X \geq 65$	3	2,70%
Total (n)		111	100%

Assumption Test

Before conducting hypothesis testing, researchers meticulously conducted assumption tests. The comprehensive assumption tests carried out by researchers included normality, linearity, and multicollinearity tests. The normality test was carried out using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. Based on the normality test results displayed in Table 6, the significance of the residual value of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking with problematic Internet use is 0.848 ($p > 0.05$). This thorough process ensures that the data is normally distributed, adding to the credibility of the study.

Table 6

Normality test result data

Variables	K-SZ	Sig. (2-tailed)
<i>Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking on problematic Internet use</i>	0.612	0.848

After conducting a normality test, researchers conducted a linearity test using the Anova technique. Based on the results of the linearity test displayed in Table 7, it can be concluded that the variables of Loneliness and problematic Internet use and Sensation-Seeking and problematic Internet use form a linear relationship because the F-Deviation from linearity is in the insignificant range ($F = 1.014$; $p > 0.05$) and ($F = 1.442$; $p > 0.05$).

Table 7

Linearity Test Result Data

Variables	F	Sig.
<i>Loneliness and PIU</i>	1.014	0.463
<i>Sensation-Seeking and PIU</i>	1.442	0.99

Then, the researchers conducted a multicollinearity test; it was found that the tolerance value for the Loneliness and Sensation variables was $0.936 > 0.10$, and the VIF value was $1.068 < 10$. Based on these results, it can be concluded that there are no multicollinearity symptoms in the regression model.

Table 8

Multicollinearity Test Result Data

Variables	Tolerance	VIF
<i>Loneliness</i>	0.936	1.068
<i>Sensation-Seeking</i>	0.936	1.068

Dependent variable : Problematic Internet use

The Relationship of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking with Problematic Internet Use

Based on the results of the correlation test using Pearson's Product Moment of 111 research subjects displayed in Table 9, it can be seen that there is a significant positive relationship between Loneliness and PIU and also between Sensation-Seeking and PIU in unmarried early adults.

Table 9

Correlation Test Result Data

	<i>Loneliness</i>	<i>Sensation-Seeking</i>	<i>PIU</i>
<i>Loneliness</i>	1		
<i>Sensation-Seeking</i>	0,252	1	
<i>PIU</i>	0,424	0,234	1

The correlation coefficient of Loneliness with PIU in unmarried early adults is 0.424, with a significance level of less than 0.01. This shows that there is a significant positive relationship between Loneliness and problematic Internet use in early unmarried adults. Similarly, the correlation between Sensation-Seeking and PIU is 0.234 with a significance level of less than 0.01. This shows that there is a significant positive relationship between Sensation-Seeking and problematic Internet use in unmarried early adults.

Hypothesis Test

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the significance coefficient value on the Loneliness variable is 0.00 ($p < 0.05$) with β 0.390 or 39% of its influence on problematic Internet use. Then, the coefficient of significance on the Sensation-Seeking variable is 0.132 ($p > 0.05$), or it can be said that it has no influence on problematic Internet use.

Furthermore, the F value is 13.232, and the significance coefficient is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). The results of this analysis also show an R Square of 0.197, which means that Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking have a joint influence of 19.7% on problematic Internet use in unmarried early adults, and as much as 80.3% is influenced by other factors outside this study. The R-value is 0.444 (< 0.7), which indicates that the closeness of the relationship between Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking to PIU is weak.

Table 10
Regression Coefficient of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking on Problematic Internet Use

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	13.324	7.097		1.878	.063
1 <i>Loneliness</i>	.542	.124	.390	4.372	.000
<i>Sensation-Seeking</i>	.163	.107	.135	1.519	.132

Table 11
Regression Test Results

F	Sig.	P	R	R Square
13,232	0.000	≤ 0.05	0.444	0.197

This study was conducted to obtain empirical results regarding the effect of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking on problematic Internet use in unmarried early adults. Gierveld (in Myers & Twenge, 2017) states that in early adulthood, Loneliness is often experienced by unmarried people. Loneliness itself is one of the factors that influence problematic Internet use (Dalton & Cassidy, 2021). This happens because using the Internet for online communication can provide benefits, including reducing feelings of isolation, stress, and panic (Holmes et al., 2020).

Based on hypothesis testing conducted on 111 unmarried early adult social media users using multiple regression analysis, the F value obtained is 13.232, and the significance coefficient is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). In general, Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking simultaneously influence problematic Internet use in unmarried early adults. The results of this analysis also show an R Square value of 0.197, which means that the variables of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking have an influence of 19.7% on problematic Internet use in unmarried early adults.

Based on the results of this study, it can be seen that individuals who feel lonely and tend to engage in problematic Internet use or can be said to have difficulty in controlling Internet use in the case of social media, which results in negative influences in everyday life. The results of this study are in line with several previous studies which state that there is a significant effect of Loneliness on problematic Internet use and social media addiction (Costa et al., 2018; Savci & Aysan, 2018; Sari, 2022) but in this study, there is no significant effect of Sensation-Seeking on problematic Internet use.

Research by Caplan and High (Garvin, 2019) found that using the Internet is one way for individuals to deal with their life problems because the Internet provides entertainment for its users. Added research conducted by Costa et al. (2018) found that individuals who experience Loneliness will prefer to utilize social contact by using the Internet.

Social media can be a medium of communication and interaction that provides opportunities for lonely individuals to establish online relationships to compensate for the lack of engagement with others offline or face-to-face. The use of social media can even become the main way for lonely individuals to engage with others (Clayton et al., 2013), and this can result in increased time accessing social media to involve individuals in social media addiction (Al-Menayes, 2015; Savci & Aysan, 2018). The use of the Internet, especially social media, which is a substitute for face-to-face social interaction, can cause individuals to experience problematic Internet use. As explained by (Weiten & Lloyd, 2006), individuals who feel lonely will use the Internet more often, causing interference in their daily functions. As seen in the demographic data, unmarried early adult individuals tend to spend more than 6 hours using social media; this will certainly make the individual more isolated from real life.

This study did not show a significant effect of Sensation-Seeking on problematic Internet use. These results are supported by the research by Lavin et al. (1999), which states that the relationship between Internet dependence and Sensation-Seeking has a low score. This is because dependence on Internet interaction uses a different motivational scheme from the physical sensations and excitement that usually characterize Sensation-Seeking. The point of the statement is that it is likely that Internet users who experience dependence tend to be very sociable but not at the point of seeking sensation. Sensation-Seeking dependent Internet users, instead of seeking sensation through physical activities, are more interested in non-physical activities (Ayuningtyas & Amawidyati, 2021).

CONCLUSION

This study shows that early adults aged 22-33 years who are unmarried tend to experience feelings of Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking and use the Internet to access most social media for more than 6 hours per day, usually done at night. Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking in this study can jointly influence problematic Internet use. Loneliness and Sensation-Seeking cause unmarried early adult individuals to prefer online social interaction over face-to-face (offline). This is because social media is a platform that provides a lot of entertainment, so unmarried early adults tend to choose to spend their time using social media to interact and communicate with other users or to view content. By itself, Sensation-Seeking does not influence problematic Internet use; this happens because Sensation-Seeking individuals tend to enjoy the pleasure of physical and in-person activities more.

SUGGESTION

For future research, it is recommended to conduct more specific research on problematic Internet use on the use of social media, such as specifically on Instagram users, Twitter, and so on. Future researchers could explore other factors that may contribute to this behavior, such as aggression, psychological well-being, procrastination, and others. In addition, future researchers are also advised to add demographic data to the questionnaire, such as the reasons for using social media to reveal more factual data. These findings suggest the need for interventions that address Loneliness in early adults to prevent or reduce problematic Internet use.

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